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MICROBIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF WIDESPREAD DRUG-RESISTANT PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS

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ANNOTATION

The massiveness of bacterial excretion in pulmonary tuberculosis is an indirect indicator reflecting the cavity character of changes in lung tissue and the density of the bacterial population. A prospective examination of 135 patients with extensively drug-resistant (XDR) pulmonary tuberculosis was conducted. The study included 68 men (45.8%) and 147 women (67%) aged 18 to 65 years. The bacteriological characteristics of XDR-TB of the lungs in the group of previously treated patients were significantly more pronounced in most parameters.

Keywords: microbiological features, drug resistance, pulmonary tuberculosis.

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МИКРОБИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕЧЕНИЯ ШИРОКО РАСПРОСТРАНЕННОГО ЛЕКАРСТВЕННО-УСТОЙЧИВОГО ТУБЕРКУЛЁЗА ЛЁГКИХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Массивность бактериовыделения при туберкулёзе лёгких является косвенным показателем, отражающим кавернозный характер изменений в лёгочной ткани и плотность бактериальной популяции. Проведено проспективное обследование 135 пациентов с широко лекарственно-устойчивым (ШЛУ) туберкулёзом лёгких. В исследование включены 68 мужчин (45,8%) и 147 женщин (67%) в возрасте от 18 до 65 лет. Бактериологические характеристики ШЛУ-туберкулёза лёгких в группе ранее леченных пациентов были значительно более выражены по большинству параметров.

Ключевые слова: микробиологические особенности, лекарственная устойчивость, туберкулёз лёгких

SAYFUTDINOV Zayniddin Asamudinovich
Tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini oshirish markazi

KENG TARQALGAN DORIGA CHIDAMLI O'PKA SILINING MIKROBIOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

O'pka silida bakteriyalarni ko'p miqdorda ajratilishi o'pka to'qimasidagi kavernozi o'zgarishlarni va bakterial populyatsiyaning zichligini aks ettiruvchi bilvosita ko'rsatkich hisoblanadi. Keng tarqalgan dori-darmonlarga chidamli (XDR) o'pka sili bilan kasallangan 135 bemor prospektiv ravishda tekshirildi. Tadqiqotga 18 yoshdan 65 yoshgacha bo'lgan 68 nafar erkak (45,8%) va 147 nafar ayol (67%) kiritildi. Oldindan davolangan bemorlar guruhida o'pka XDR-silining bakteriologik xususiyatlari ko'pgina parametrlar bo'yicha sezilarli darajada aniqroq edi.

Kalit so'zlar: mikrobiologik xususiyatlar, dori-darmonlarga chidamlilik, o'pka sili.

Introduction. World and domestic statistics clearly indicate an increase in the problem of tuberculosis with multiple (MDR) and broad drug resistance (BDR) of mycobacterium tuberculosis (MBT) [6]. According to official Russian statistics, for the period 2019-2020, the proportion of MDR-TB patients among newly diagnosed patients and all bacterial isolators with respiratory tuberculosis continued to grow - 32.9-34.0% and 59.9-64.5%, respectively.

According to official statistics, the proportion of BDR-TB patients in the Russian Federation is 18.9% of all reported MDR-TB cases and ranges from 4.4 to 10.2% among new MDR-TB cases, 7.4-13.3% – with relapses of MDR-TB, 18.5-30.8% – in patients re-starting treatment with MDR-TB [2]. At the same time, the analytical review of the main indicators of anti-tuberculosis work in 2018-2019 provides data on an increase in the number of cases of BDR MBT registered for treatment (before the start of chemotherapy) from 4,775 to 5,347 people. Based on the proportion, this amounted to 36.3% relative to the registered cases of newly diagnosed patients and cases of treatment of recurrent tuberculosis with MDR MBT. The indicators of official statistics on tuberculosis with BDR pathogen in the domestic and world literature have been absent for a long time. At the same time, it is known that BDR-MBT infection is subject to fundamentally different epidemiological patterns of spread and accumulation in nature and society. It has been established that the elimination of BDR-TB patients from the epidemiological cohort is much slower, unlike patients with other drug resistance spectra of the pathogen, especially drug-sensitive tuberculosis [4].

The massiveness of bacterial excretion in pulmonary tuberculosis is an indirect indicator reflecting the cavity character of changes in lung tissue and the density of the bacterial population. Bacterial excretion and its massiveness are affected by bronchial patency. The dynamics of bacterial massiveness reflects the effectiveness of chemotherapy. However, it is necessary to take into account the heterogeneity of the mycobacterial population, which can provoke the effect of "false positive dynamics" [1]. Studies have shown that even with BDR-TB, there are MBTs in the cavern population that remain sensitive to certain chemotherapy drugs or their lower critical concentrations [5]. It is these MBTs that will be eliminated in the first place, demonstrating a decrease in the massiveness of bacterial excretion. The bacteriological phenomenon of "rise and fall" is known in the phthisiological literature, when positive sputum tests reappear after the cessation of bacterial excretion as the resistant population of the pathogen accumulates [7]. In BDR-TB, special attention should be paid to such phenomena reflecting the insufficient effectiveness of chemotherapy. "False positive" results of bacteriological studies, masking latent drug resistance, may unreasonably delay the adoption of adequate decisions on changing the chemotherapy regimen or resolving the issue of surgical treatment. At the same time, the indicator of bacterial massiveness remains relevant in the overall assessment of the clinical picture of the disease [3].

Research materials and methods. A prospective examination of 135 patients with extensively drug-resistant (XDR) pulmonary tuberculosis was conducted. The study included 68 men (45.8%) and 147 women (67%) aged 18 to 65 years.

Sputum examination included luminescent microscopy, inoculation on dense and liquid nutrient media with determination of drug sensitivity, methods of molecular genetic identification of MBT with determination of genetic markers of drug resistance of the pathogen. Sputum cultures were

carried out on liquid nutrient media using the automated BACTEC 960 MGIT method and determination of drug sensitivity to first-line anti-tuberculosis drugs; on dense Levenstein – Jensen nutrient media with a transfer to a medium for determining the drug sensitivity (DS) of MBT by the method of absolute concentrations. Bacterial excretion was assessed using luminescent microscopy and the seeding method. The culture of the pathogen was considered sensitive to critical concentrations of chemotherapy drugs if less than 20 colonies grew in a test tube with abundant growth in a control tube.

Critical concentrations were considered: streptomycin – 10 mcg/ml, isoniazid – 1 mcg/ml and 10 mcg/ml, rifampicin – 40 mcg/ml, kanamycin – 30 mcg/ml, ethionamide/protionamide – 30 mcg/ml, ethambutol – 2 mcg/ml, cycloserine – 30 mcg/ml, ofloxacin – 4 mcg/ ml, capreomycin – 30 mcg / ml. The following gradations of bacterial massiveness were taken into account by the seeding method: meager – growth from 1 to 20 colony-forming units (CFU), moderate – growth from 21 to 100 CFU, abundant - growth of more than 100 CFU. The luminescent microscopy data were evaluated according to the following indicators: meager – 10-99 acid-resistant mycobacteria (ARM) in 100 fields of view, moderate – 1-10 CUM in 1 field of view, abundant – more than 10 ARM in 1 field of view.

The cessation of bacterial excretion was counted from the month during which the first negative results of bacterioscopy and seeding were obtained, subject to further negative results.

The spectra of drug resistance (DR) of the pathogen and drug resistance of the pathogen in patients of different groups and categories to individual chemotherapy drugs were studied. In total, 22 different variants of the MBT DR spectra were observed.

Statistical processing of the obtained data was performed using Statsoft. STATISTICA 10 and Microsoft Excel 2016 software. The study of the relationship between the indicators of treatment safety and the frequency of adverse events was carried out using correlation analysis with the determination of rank nonparametric Spearman correlation coefficients.

The results. The results of assessing the degree of bacterial excretion according to the method of luminescent microscopy and seeding on liquid nutrient media are presented in tab. 1.

Table 1

The massiveness of bacterial excretion in XDR/TB patients of different registration groups

Group of patients	Number of patients	Luminal microscopy of sputum		Sputum sowing	
		MBT massiveness (+)		MBT massiveness (+)	
		Meager	Massive	Meager	Massive
Newly identified	25	18	7	16	9
%		72% a b	28% c d	64% e f	36% g h
Previously treated	100	28	73	30	70
		28% a	73% c	30% e	70% g
Relapse	10	4	6	2	8
%		40% a	60% d	20% f	80% h
Total	135	50	85	59	74
%	100%	37% ±4,8	63% ±3,6	43,7% ±4,5	54,8% ±4,0

Note: a-a; b-b; c-c; d-d; e-e; f-f; g-g; h-h – the difference is statistically significant, p<0.05

From the data presented in Table 1, it follows that poor bacterial excretion was overwhelmingly observed in newly diagnosed patients – according to luminescent microscopy in 18 people (72%), according to the seeding method – in 16 (64%) patients. Massive bacterial excretion statistically significantly prevailed among patients with repeated courses of chemotherapy – according to luminescent microscopy in 73 people (73%), according to the seeding method – in 70 (70%) patients. In patients with relapses of the disease, massive bacterial excretion was observed

much more often - according to luminescent microscopy in 6 people (60%), according to the seeding method – in 8 (80%) patients.

In newly diagnosed patients, the spectra of LU with less additional drug resistance prevailed. In 23 (92%) newly diagnosed patients with BDR pathogen, additional resistance was available to a maximum of three chemotherapy drugs. More "broad" spectra of MBT were observed in the group of patients with repeated treatment. Additional resistance to the 2nd, 3rd and 4th drugs during repeated treatment was noted, respectively, in 18 (18%), 30 (30%) and 30 (30%) patients. In patients with relapses, the leading position was occupied by a spectrum of drugs with additional resistance to 3 CP – 3 patients (30%). The most common combinations among all observed patients were: BDR+3 CP – 40 patients (29.6%); BDR+4 CP – 32 patients (23.7%); BDR+2 CP – 27 patients (20%).

The diagram in Fig. 1 clearly shows the spectra of additional drug resistance in BDR-TB patients in different registration groups.

Figure 1. Spectra of additional DR in BDR-TB patients of different registration groups

The data presented in the diagram in Fig. 1. show that in newly diagnosed patients, combinations of BDR+1 spectra prevailed statistically significantly compared with other groups ($p < 0.05$). Combinations of BDR+2; BDR+3 and BDR+4 were statistically more common in previously treated and relapsed patients compared with newly diagnosed patients ($p < 0.05$).

Drug resistance to certain chemotherapy drugs in different categories of patients is shown in the diagram in Figure 2. From the data presented in the diagram in Fig. 2, it follows that in the spectra of additional resistance in newly diagnosed patients, ethambutol (40.8%), pyrazinamide (38.8%), protionamide (38.8%), PASC (30.6%) prevailed. In previously treated patients, drug resistance was more often observed to pyrazinamide (75%), ethambutol (70%), PASC (55%), protionamide (48%). In relapses, the highest proportion of resistance was noted to pyrazinamide (60%), ethambutol (60%), PASC (60%), protionamide (52.4%). Resistance to fourth-generation fluoroquinolones was observed in 40.8% of newly diagnosed, 50% of previously treated and 50% of patients with relapses.

Figure 2. Additional drug resistance of BDR-MBT to individual CP in patients in different registration groups

Calculations show that the established spectra of additional drug resistance of the BDR pathogen make it possible to provide a combination of 5 chemotherapy drugs with preserved sensitivity of the pathogen in 63.3% of newly diagnosed patients, 31% of previously treated patients, and 40% of patients with recurrent TB.

Conclusion. Thus, the bacteriological characteristics of BDR-TB of the lungs in the group of previously treated patients were significantly more pronounced in most parameters, which significantly limited the potential of conservative measures and the prognosis of the disease largely depended on the possibilities of additional methods of complex treatment, including surgical methods.

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